

(a)

(b)

(c)

(d)

Figure S1. Spatial distribution of the change in (a) Aerosol Optical Depth (AOD) at 550nm, (b) Tropospheric Ozone (O_3) column (DU), (c) Total Cloud Cover (%), and (d) Surface Albedo caused by the present-day wildfire emissions compared to the corresponding pre-industrial era.

The maps depict the difference between the 10-year mean of the pre-industrial simulations and the 10-year mean of the present-day simulations. Black hatching denotes that the change is significant at the 0.05 level.